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Research Article

**VALIDATED RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT FOR THE
ESTIMATION OF DECITABINE & CEDAZURIDINE IN ITS
COMBINED DOSAGE FORMS.****A. Mahesh*, Mrs. K. Radhika, R. Madhulika, Dr. K. Shravankumar**¹Department Of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Samskruti College Of Pharmacy, Ghatkesar,
Telangana. 501301.**Article Received: August 2024****Accepted: September 2024****Published: October 2024****Abstract:**

A new, simple, rapid and precise reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed for the validation of Decitabine and Cedazuridine in its pure form as well as in combined marketed formulation. Chromatography was carried out on a Phenomenex Luna C18 (4.6mm×250mm) 5µm particle size column using a mixture of Methanol: Water (45:55% v/v) as the mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0ml/min, the detection was carried out at 240nm. The retention time of the Decitabine and Cedazuridine was found to be was 2.133, 3.692 ± 0.02min respectively. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines for linearity, sensitivity, accuracy, precision, specificity and robustness. The method produce linear responses in the concentration range of 20-60mg/ml of Decitabine and 10-30mg/ml of Cedazuridine. The inter-day and intra-day precisions were found to be within limits. The method precision for the determination of assay was below 2.0%RSD. The method is useful in the quality control of bulk and pharmaceutical formulations.

Keywords: *Decitabine and Cedazuridine, RP-HPLC, Validation, Accuracy, Precision.***Corresponding author:****A.Mahesh,**

Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,

Samskruti college of pharmacy,

Ghatkesar, Telangana.

Email Id- maheshavirendral@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Analytic method development and validation are key elements of any pharmaceutical development program. HPLC analysis method is developed to identify, quantify or purifying compounds of interest. This technical brief will focus on development and validation activities as applied to drug products.

Method development:

Effective method development ensures that laboratory resources are optimized, while methods meet the objectives required at each stage of drug development. Method validation, required by regulatory agencies at certain stages of the drug approval process, is defined as the “process of demonstrating that analytical procedures are suitable for their intended use” [1-2]. Understanding of the physical and chemical characteristics of drug allows one to select the most appropriate high performance liquid chromatography method development from the available vast literature. Information concerning the sample, for example, molecular mass, structure and functionality, pKa values and UV spectra, solubility of compound should be compiled. The requirement of removal of insoluble impurities by filtration, centrifugation, dilution or concentration to control the concentration, extraction (liquid or solid phase), derivatization for detection etc. should be checked. For pure compound, the sample solubility should be identified whether it is organic solvent soluble or water soluble, as this helps to select the best mobile phase and column to be used in HPLC method development.

Method development in HPLC can be laborious and time consuming. Chromatographers may spend many hours trying to optimize a separation on a column to accomplish the goals. Even among reversed phase columns, there is astonishing diversity, owing to differences in both base silica and bonded phase characteristics. Many of these show unique selectivity. What is needed is a more informed decision making process for column selection that may be used before the chromatographer enters the laboratory. The method of column selection presented here involves a minimal investment in time initially, with the potential of saving many hours in the laboratory.

Analytic methods are intended to establish the identity, purity, physical characteristics and potency of the drugs that we use. Methods are developed to support drug testing against specifications during manufacturing and quality release operations, as well as during long-term stability studies. Methods that

support safety and characterization studies or evaluations of drug performance are also to be evaluated. Once a stability-indicating method is in place, the formulated drug product can then be subjected to heat and light in order to evaluate the potential degradation of the API in the presence of formulation excipients [3, 4].

The three critical components for a HPLC method are: sample preparation (% organic, pH, shaking/sonication, sample size, sample age) analysis conditions (%organic, pH, flow rate, temperature, wavelength, and column age), and standardization (integration, wavelength, standard concentration, and response factor correction). During the preliminary method development stage, all individual components should be investigated before the final method optimization. This gives the scientist a chance to critically evaluate the method performance in each component and streamline the final method optimization [5]. The percentage of time spent on each stage is proposed to ensure the scientist will allocate sufficient time to different steps. In this approach, the three critical components for a HPLC method (sample preparation, HPLC analysis and standardization) will first be investigated individually [6-8].

The degraded drug samples obtained are subjected to preliminary chromatographic separation to study the number and types of degradation products formed under various conditions [9]. Scouting experiments are run and then conditions are chosen for further optimization [10]. Resolving power, specificity, and speed are key chromatographic method attributes to keep in mind during method development [11]. Selectivity can be manipulated by combination of different factors like solvent composition, type of stationary phase, mobile phase, buffers and pH. Changing solvents and stationary phases are the most comfortable approaches to achieve the separation. The proper range of pH is an important tool for separation of ionizable compounds. Acidic compounds are retained at low pH while basic compounds are more retained at higher pH. The neutral compounds remain unaffected. The pH range 4-8 is not generally employed because slight change in pH in this range would result in a dramatic shift in retention time. However, by operating at pH extremes (2-4 or 8-10), not only is there a 10-30 fold difference in retention time that can be exploited in method development but also the method can be made more robust which is a desirable outcome with validation in minutes. Various steps for HPLC method development are given below.

Requirements for good method development:**Choosing the appropriate HPLC column:**

C18 columns are the commonly used columns in HPLC method analysis. C8 or Octyl bonded phases are also used occasionally. Like C18, they are non-polar, but not as hydrophobic. Therefore, retention times for hydrophobic compounds are typically shorter. Also, they may show somewhat different selectivity than C18 due to increased base silica exposure unique selectivity results in proton interaction of the bonded phase with electron deficient functional groups of solute molecules.

Retention is a mixed mechanism, resulting from both hydrophobic interactions and dipole interactions of the bonded phase C-N group with solute amino groups or p - p interactions with sites of unsaturation. It is the best for polar organic compounds and is versatile enough for use in both normal and reversed phase modes.

Each bonded phase has unique selectivity for certain sample types. For example: to separate toluene and ethyl benzene (differ by only one -CH₂- unit), we would choose a C18 bonded phase. Further, we would want to narrow the decision to a particular packing material that shows good or excellent retention of such hydrophobic compounds (i.e. high % carbon load) to be able to maximize the particular separation. The effects of surface area and carbon load are discussed in the next section. The stationary phase must be able to "hold on" to the two compounds long enough to resolve them.

Column Dimensions:

This refers to the length and internal diameter of the packing media bed within the column tube. Short columns (30-50mm) offer short run times, fast equilibration, low back pressure and high sensitivity. Long columns (250-300mm) provide higher resolving power, but create more backpressure, lengthen analysis times and use more solvent. Narrow column (2.1mm and smaller) beds inhibit sample diffusion and produce narrower, taller peaks and a lower limit of detection. They may require instrument modification to minimize distortion of the chromatography. Wider columns (10-22mm) offer the ability to load more sample.

Particle shape:

Most modern chromatographic packings have spherical particles, but some are irregular in shape. Spherical particles offer reduced back pressures and longer column life when using viscous mobile phases like 50:50 MeOH: H₂O.

Particle Size:

This refers to the average diameter of the packing media particles. Standard particle sizes range from 3µm (high efficiency) to 15-20µm (preparative). A 5µm particle size offers a good compromise between efficiency and back pressure. Smaller particles pack into columns with a higher density, allowing less diffusion of sample bands between particles and causing narrower, sharper peaks. However, smaller particles also cause higher solvent back pressures. As a rule of thumb, 1.5 or 3µm particle sizes are to be chosen for resolving complex, multi-component samples. Otherwise, 5 or 10µm packings should be considered.

Surface area:

Expressed in m²/gram, the total surface area of a particle is the sum of the outer particle surface and the interior pore surface. Solute retention is greater on packings that have a high surface area. High surface areas generally provide longer retention, greater capacity and higher resolution. As a rule of thumb, a base material with maximum surface area is to be used for resolving complex and multi-component samples.

Pore size:

This refers to the average size of the pores or cavities present in porous packing particles. Pore sizes range from 60Å on the low end to greater than 10,000Å on the high end. Larger pores allow larger solute molecules to be retained longer through maximum exposure to the surface area of the particles. A pore size of 150Å or less is chosen for sample MW < 2000. For sample with molecular weight greater than 2000, columns with a pore size of 300Å or greater are to be used.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Decitabine-Procured from Sun pharma, provided by Sura Pharma labs, Cedazuridine-Procured from Sun pharma, provided by Sura Pharma labs, Water and Methanol for HPLC-LICHROSOLV (MERCK), Acetonitrile for HPLC-

Merck, Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate-Finar Chemicals.

Hplc method development:**Trails****Preparation of standard solution:**

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Decitabine & Cedazuridine working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and

sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol. Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Decitabine and 0.3ml of the Cedazuridine stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

Mobile Phase Optimization:

Initially the mobile phase tried was Methanol: Water and Water: Acetonitrile and Methanol: Phosphate Buffer: ACN with varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was optimized to Acetonitrile: Water in proportion 45:55 v/v respectively.

Optimization of Column:

The method was performed with various columns like C18 column, Symmetry and Zodiac column. Phenomenex Luna C18 (4.6×250mm, 5µm) particle size was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 1ml/min flow.

Optimized chromatographic conditions:

Instrument used : Waters HPLC with auto sampler and PDA Detector 996 model.
Temperature : 35°C

Column : Phenomenex Luna C18 (4.6×250mm, 5µm) particle size
Mobile phase : Acetonitrile: Water (45:55 v/v)
Flow rate : 1ml/min
Wavelength : 240 nm
Injection volume : 10 µl
Run time : 6 min

Validation

Preparation of buffer and mobile phase:

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 450 ml (45%) of Methanol, 550 ml of Water (55%) were mixed and degassed in digital ultra sonicator for 15 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 µ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Mobile phase ratio : Methanol: Water (45:55 v/v)
Column : Phenomenex Luna C18 (4.6mm×250mm) 5µm particle size
Column temperature : 35°C
Wavelength : 240nm
Flow rate : 1ml/min
Injection volume : 10µl
Run time : 6minutes

Figure: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Table: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

S.No.	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Resolution
1	Decitabine	2.133	526388	86757	1.57	5678	
2	Cedazuridine	3.692	1687286	367533	1.78	8686	9.9

Observation: From the above chromatogram it was observed that the Cedazuridine and Decitabine peaks are well separated and they show proper retention time, resolution, peak tail and plate count. So, it's optimized trial.

Optimized Chromatogram**Figure: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)****Table: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)**

S.No.	Name	Rt	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Resolution
1	Decitabine	2.166	536588	77465	1.58	5788	
2	Cedazuridine	3.629	1695847	378563	1.81	8796	10.02

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2.
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000.
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

System Suitability:**Table:- Results of system suitability for Decitabine**

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area (μV*sec)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Decitabine	2.152	526359	86599	5696	1.58
2	Decitabine	2.157	526547	86255	5653	1.59
3	Decitabine	2.141	526853	86600	5628	1.58
4	Decitabine	2.133	526597	86246	5693	1.59
5	Decitabine	2.166	524878	86522	5642	1.58
Mean			526246.8			
Std. Dev.			785.2453			
% RSD			0.149216			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Table:- Results of system suitability for Cedazuridine

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Resolution
1	Cedazuridine	3.674	1682822	1686959	8658	1.56	9.8
2	Cedazuridine	3.631	1682727	1685746	8676	1.57	9.9
3	Cedazuridine	3.625	1687362	1685422	8693	1.56	9.8
4	Cedazuridine	3.692	1682812	1685243	8641	1.57	9.8
5	Cedazuridine	3.629	1683817	1685365	8636	1.58	9.8
Mean			1683908				
Std. Dev.			1982.03				
% RSD			0.117704				

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Assay (Standard):**Table: Peak results for assay standard of Decitabine**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Decitabine	2.152	526357	86599	1.55	5699	1
2	Decitabine	2.198	526585	86783	1.58	5688	2
3	Decitabine	2.179	529659	86254	1.56	5638	3

Table: Peak results for assay standard of Cedazuridine

S.No.	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Cedazuridine	3.646	1687588	365878	1.80	8658	1
2	Cedazuridine	3.604	1685986	365853	1.79	8696	2
3	Cedazuridine	3.610	1685973	369855	1.80	8674	3

Assay (Sample):**Table: Peak results for Assay sample of Decitabine**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Decitabine	2.152	536858	87583	1.58	5788	1
2	Decitabine	2.150	532653	87964	1.59	5783	2
3	Decitabine	2.187	532684	87466	1.58	5768	3

Table: Peak results for Assay sample of Cedazuridine

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Cedazuridine	3.646	1698569	378563	1.81	8758	1
2	Cedazuridine	3.651	1698573	375848	1.80	8796	2
3	Cedazuridine	3.601	1698548	376585	1.81	8744	3

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

= 99.89%

The % purity of Cedazuridine & Decitabine in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 99.89%

Linearity

Chromatographic data for linearity study:

Table:- Chromatographic Data for Linearity Study of Decitabine

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
20	272898
30	402987
40	526388
50	649786
60	769288

Fig: Calibration Curve of Decitabine

Table-: Chromatographic Data for Linearity Study of Cedazuridine

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
10	1000238
15	1448769
20	1887286
25	2365898
30	2826846

Fig: Calibration Curve of Cedazuridine**Repeatability:****Table: Results of repeatability for Decitabine:**

S. No.	Peak Name	Retention time	Area (µV*sec)	Height (µV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Decitabine	2.157	526359	86599	5688	1.56
2	Decitabine	2.159	524857	86543	5686	1.57
3	Decitabine	2.186	526986	86579	5685	1.56
4	Decitabine	2.160	528653	86355	5679	1.56
5	Decitabine	2.170	528456	86959	5638	1.56
Mean			527063			
Std.dev			1568.114			
%RSD			0.297708			

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Table: Results of Repeatability for Cedazuridine:

S. No.	Peak Name	Retention time	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Cedazuridine	3.603	1687588	367858	8658	1.79
2	Cedazuridine	3.608	1685986	368546	8677	1.80
3	Cedazuridine	3.600	1685988	367984	8646	1.80
4	Cedazuridine	3.696	1685753	365873	8694	1.79
5	Cedazuridine	3.629	1685986	364588	8627	1.79
Mean			1686260			
Std.Dev			749.493			
%RSD			0.044447			

Intermediate precision:**Table: Results of Intermediate precision for Decitabine**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	%Assay
1	Decitabine	2.198	546586	87588	5899	1.58	100%
2	Decitabine	2.196	548757	87986	5878	1.59	100%
3	Decitabine	2.160	549855	87453	5869	1.58	100%
4	Decitabine	2.160	548799	87422	5848	1.59	100%
5	Decitabine	2.160	542658	87964	5897	1.58	100%
6	Decitabine	2.186	548755	87253	5875	1.59	100%
Mean			547569				
Std. Dev.			2632.576				
% RSD			0.480594				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table: Results of Intermediate precision for Cedazuridine

S.No.	Peak Name	Rt	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing	Resolution	%Assay
1	Cedazuridine	3.623	1698588	385483	8788	1.81	9.8	98%
2	Cedazuridine	3.611	1698575	385699	8757	1.80	9.8	98.1%
3	Cedazuridine	3.696	1698533	385747	8755	1.81	9.9	98.8%
4	Cedazuridine	3.696	1698575	386959	8756	1.81	10.01	99.8%
5	Cedazuridine	3.696	1698533	385756	8799	1.80	9.98	98.6%
6	Cedazuridine	3.642	1698548	386559	8763	1.80	10.02	98.3%
Mean			1698559					
Std. Dev.			23.77114					
% RSD			0.001398					

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table:- Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Decitabine

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area (µV*sec)	Height (µV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Decitabine	2.198	536855	8757	5788	1.58
2	Decitabine	2.196	536986	8796	5727	1.59
3	Decitabine	2.178	536588	8747	5743	1.58
4	Decitabine	2.142	532547	8753	5747	1.59
5	Decitabine	2.177	534588	8726	5799	1.58
6	Decitabine	2.177	538599	8727	5786	1.59
Mean			536027.2			
Std. Dev.			2132.492			
% RSD			0.397648			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Table:- Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Cedazuridine

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area (µV*sec)	Height (µV)	USP Plate	USP Tailing	Resolution
1	Cedazuridine	3.611	1678599	356876	8876	1.82	9.9
2	Cedazuridine	3.623	1678986	358984	8857	1.83	10.01
3	Cedazuridine	3.684	1678983	358753	8863	1.82	9.9
4	Cedazuridine	3.697	1678986	352414	8848	1.83	10.01
5	Cedazuridine	3.684	1678548	358988	8874	1.82	9.9
6	Cedazuridine	3.684	1678985	358987	8843	1.83	10.01
Mean			1678849				
Std. Dev.			213.8048				
% RSD			0.012677				

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Accuracy:**Table: The accuracy results for Decitabine**

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	267012.3	20	20.064	100.316%	100.29%
100%	523753.3	40	40.119	100.296%	
150%	778458.3	60	60.134	100.222%	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

Table: The accuracy results for Cedazuridine

% Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	972876.3	10	10.094	100.94%	100.48%
100%	1900122	20	19.998	99.99%	
150%	2851152	30	30.156	100.52%	

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

Robustness**Decitabine:**

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	526388	2.133	5678	1.56
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	542686	2.210	5263	1.54
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	526484	2.184	5427	1.52
Less organic phase	516855	2.200	5164	1.57
More Organic phase	506899	2.172	5099	1.51

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

Cedazuridine:

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	1687286	3.692	8686	1.78
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	1725469	4.498	8267	1.69
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	1652848	3.505	8416	1.58
Less organic phase	1687486	4.504	8327	1.61
More organic phase	1674523	3.512	8416	1.63

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

CONCLUSION:

In this study, a new RP-HPLC method was developed and validated for the simultaneous quantification of Decitabine and Cedazuridine in both their pure forms and combined marketed formulations. Chromatographic separation was achieved using a Phenomenex Luna C18 column with a mobile phase consisting of Methanol and Water (45:55% v/v), flowing at a rate of 1.0 ml/min, and detection was performed at 240 nm. The retention times observed for Decitabine and Cedazuridine were 2.133 and 3.692 ± 0.02 minutes, respectively.

The method was rigorously validated following ICH guidelines, covering key parameters such as linearity,

sensitivity, accuracy, precision, specificity, and robustness. The calibration curves demonstrated linear responses over the concentration ranges of 20-60 mg/ml for Decitabine and 10-30 mg/ml for Cedazuridine. Both inter-day and intra-day precision studies indicated consistent results within acceptable limits, with method precision for assay determination yielding below 2.0% RSD.

Overall, this newly developed RP-HPLC method offers a straightforward, rapid, and precise approach for the quantitative analysis of Decitabine and Cedazuridine, making it suitable for routine quality control applications in bulk drug manufacturing and pharmaceutical formulations.

The validated RP-HPLC method presented in this study provides a reliable means for the simultaneous estimation of Decitabine and Cedazuridine in their individual and combined dosage forms. The method's robustness, demonstrated by its ability to separate and quantify both compounds efficiently and accurately, meets the stringent criteria set forth by ICH guidelines. The observed linear responses, excellent precision, and low method variability underscore its suitability for use in pharmaceutical quality control laboratories. By offering simplicity and rapid analysis without compromising precision, this method ensures dependable results essential for maintaining the quality and consistency of Decitabine and Cedazuridine formulations in the pharmaceutical industry.

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